

Timeline for Faster than the Speed of Light Technology.

Written below is the approximate period of time for Faster than the Speed of Light travel.

Period of time: 22nd century
Speed Achieved: 1.2 times the Speed of Light

Period of time: 23rd century
Speed Achieved: 1.7 times the Speed of Light

Period of time: 25th century
Speed Achieved: 2.3 times the Speed of Light

Period of time: 3rd millennium
Speed Achieved: 3.2 times

Period of time: 5th millennium
Speed Achieved: 4.7 times

Period of time: 12th millennium
Speed Achieved: 7 times

Period of time: 20th millennium
Speed Achieved: 13 times

Period of time: 50th millennium
Speed Achieved: 32 times

Period of time: 100th millennium
Speed Achieved: 79 times

Period of time: 200th millennium
Speed Achieved: 127 times

Period of time: 500th millennium
Speed Achieved: 389 times

Period of time: 1 million (year)
Speed Achieved: 895 times

Period of time: 3 million
Speed Achieved: 3.4k times

Period of time: 5 million
Speed Achieved: 7.8k times

Period of time: 10 million
Speed Achieved: 17.9k times

Period of time: 20 million
Speed Achieved: 45.7k times

Period of time: 50 million
Speed Achieved: 120k times

Period of time: 100 million
Speed Achieved: 360k

Period of time: 200 million
Speed Achieved: 840k

Period of time: 500 million
Speed Achieved: 1.2m times

Period of time: 1 billion
Speed Achieved: 5m times

Period of time: 200 billion
Speed Achieved: 1.2b times

Period of time: 1 trillion
Speed Achieved: 40b times

Period of time: 1 quadrillion
Speed Achieved: 720b times

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Albi Ndoni
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